

ASYMPTOTIC HOMOGENIZATION MODELING OF MAGNETO-ELECTRIC SMART COMPOSITES

D. A. Hadjiloizi¹, A. L. Kalamkarov^{2*}, S. Jothi¹, A.V. Georgiades^{1,3}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering and Materials Science and Engineering, Cyprus University of Technology, Lemesos, Cyprus

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Dalhousie University, Halifax, NS, Canada

³ Research Unit for Nanostructured Materials Systems, Cyprus University of Technology, Lemesos, Cyprus

* Corresponding author (Alex.Kalamkarov@dal.ca)

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1 Abstract

Comprehensive micromechanical models for the analysis of piezo-magneto-thermo-elastic smart composite structures with orthotropic constituents are presented. The first asymptotic homogenization model is derived on the basis of the dynamic force and thermal balance as well as Maxwell's equations. Subsequently general relations called unit cell problems are derived. They can be used to determine the effective elastic, piezoelectric, piezomagnetic, thermal expansion, dielectric permittivity, magnetic permeability, magnetoelectric, pyroelectric and pyromagnetic coefficients. The latter three sets of coefficients are particularly interesting in the sense that they represent product or cross-properties; they are generated in the macroscopic composite via the interaction of the different phases, but may be absent from some of the constituents themselves. The derived relations pertaining to the unit-cell problems and the resultant effective coefficients are very general and they are valid for any 3D geometry of the unit cell. Subsequently, the salient features of a second quasi-static model are outlined. The models developed are illustrated by analyzing practically important magnetoelectric laminates and 3D network-reinforced composites.

2 Introduction

Aided by rapid technological advancements in the fabrication processing and characterization of sensors, actuators and novel material systems, the incorporation of smart composites and, more

recently, smart nanocomposites in new engineering applications has sparked a renewed interest in developing new micromechanical models for predicting their effective properties at the design stage. A special class of smart composites, those composed of piezoelectric and piezomagnetic constituents, has recently attracted attention due to their interesting properties and their significant potential for new applications. Such materials exhibit the so-called product properties which are manifested in the consolidated composite but not in the individual constituents. Most important among these product properties are magnetoelectricity, pyroelectricity and pyromagnetism. As Nan et al [1] show, these properties can be conveniently presented in the form:

$$\text{Magnetoelectric Effect} = \frac{\text{Magnetic}}{\text{Mechanical}} \times \frac{\text{Mechanical}}{\text{Electric}}$$

$$\text{Pyroelectric Effect} = \frac{\text{Thermal}}{\text{Mechanical}} \times \frac{\text{Mechanical}}{\text{Electric}}$$

$$\text{Pyromagnetic Effect} = \frac{\text{Thermal}}{\text{Mechanical}} \times \frac{\text{Mechanical}}{\text{Magnetic}}$$

Thus, applying an electric field to a piezoelectric-piezomagnetic composite generates mechanical strain in the piezoelectric phase. This deformation is then transferred to the piezomagnetic phase which, in turn, generates a magnetic field. Therefore, overall, an electric field induces a magnetic field and vice-versa. This is magnetoelectricity. Similar phenomena underlie pyroelectricity and pyromagnetism.

The increased interest in such smart structures necessitates a need in further development of the

rigorous micromechanical models allowing the adequate prediction of their effective properties.

Noteworthy among the associated analytical models are the works of Harshe et al. [2], Huang et al [3], Ni et al [4], Bichurin et al [5], Bravo-Castillero et al [6], Hadjiloizi et al [7-9] and a few others.

A mathematically rigorous approach that can be effectively applied for the modeling and analysis of magneto-electric composites is the multiscale asymptotic homogenization method. Many problems in thermoelasticity and piezoelectricity have been solved using this technique, see, e.g., Kalamkarov [10,11]. The objective of this paper is to illustrate the development of an asymptotic homogenization model for the determination of the effective coefficients, including the product properties, of 3D piezoelectric-piezomagnetic composites made up of orthotropic constituents [7]. The work will be illustrated by means of the practically important thick laminates [8].

Dynamic Asymptotic Homogenization Model

2.1 Problem Formulation

Fig. 1 shows a general 3D smart composite structure representing an inhomogeneous solid occupying domain G with boundary ∂G that contains a large number of periodically arranged unit cells with characteristic dimension ε .

Fig. 1. 3D periodic smart composite

The macroscopic behaviour of this smart composite structure is modelled by the following boundary value problems, describing dynamic force and thermal balance and Maxwell's equations.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial x_j} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{\nabla} \times \bar{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t} + \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\nabla} \times \bar{\mathbf{E}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{y})\rho(\mathbf{y})\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t} \quad (4)$$

Here, σ_{ij} and u_i represent mechanical stresses and displacements, H_i and B_i are, respectively, the magnetic induction and magnetic field, D_i is the electric displacement, J_i is the free conduction current, C is the specific heat capacity, T is the temperature field, and q_i is the heat flux vector.

To complete the analysis, Eqs. (1) - (4) must be complimented with the appropriate constitutive equations shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = & C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_l}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) - e_{kij}(\mathbf{y}) E_k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \\ & - Q_{kij}(\mathbf{y}) H_k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) - \theta_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = & e_{ijk}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_j}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) E_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \\ & + \lambda_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) H_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \xi_i(\mathbf{y}) T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = & Q_{ijk}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_k}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \lambda_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) E_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \\ & + \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) H_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \eta_i(\mathbf{y}) T(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$J_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \Sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) E_j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \quad (8)$$

$$q_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = -V_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \quad (9)$$

where E_k is the electric field vector, C_{ijkl} , e_{ijk} , Q_{ijk} , and θ_{ij} are the tensors of the elastic, piezoelectric, piezomagnetic and thermal expansion coefficients respectively. As well, ε_{ij} , λ_{ij} , μ_{ij} , ξ_i , η_i , Σ_{ij} and K_{ij} represent, respectively, the dielectric permittivity, the magnetoelectric, the magnetic permeability, the pyroelectric, the pyromagnetic, the electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity tensors. The

dependence of the material coefficients and the field variables on $y_i = x_i/\varepsilon$ is a reflection of the strict periodicity of the material properties (with period ε); the field variables however, are, naturally characterized by both a periodic and a non-periodic components, see [7-11]. Variables x_i are often referred to as the “slow” or “macroscopic” variables, while their counterparts, y_i , are referred to as the “fast” or “microscopic” variables.

2.2 Asymptotic Homogenization Modeling and Unit Cell Problems

Analysis begins by asymptotically expanding the independent field variables into powers of ε . For example, the mechanical stress is expressed as:

$$\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \sigma_{ij}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \varepsilon \sigma_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + O(\varepsilon^2) \quad (10)$$

Subsequently, substituting expressions such as (10) into the constitutive equations (5)-(9) and comparing terms with the same powers of ε yields expressions for the n -th term of each asymptotic expansion. For example,

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(n)} = C_{ijkl} \left(\frac{\partial u_k^{(n)}}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial u_k^{(n+1)}}{\partial y_l} \right) - e_{kij} E_k^{(n)} - Q_{kij} H_k^{(n)} - \theta_{ij} T^{(n)}, \quad (11)$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

These asymptotic expansions are then substituted into the governing equations (1)-(4) to obtain, after comparing like powers of ε , a set of differential equations for the n -th term of each expansion. For example, the terms of the magnetic field expansion, satisfy the following differential equations [7]:

$$O(\varepsilon^n): \quad \varepsilon_{ijk} \left\{ \frac{\partial H_k^{(n)}}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial H_k^{(n+1)}}{\partial y_j} \right\} \tilde{e}_i = \frac{\partial D_k^{(n)}}{\partial t} \tilde{e}_k + J_k^{(n)} \tilde{e}_k, \quad (12)$$

$n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

It would also not be amiss to mention that in the process, it turns out that the first terms in the asymptotic expansions for mechanical displacement and temperature are independent of y and the first terms in the electric and magnetic field expansions are irrotational and can thus be expressed as the gradients of scalar fields:

$$E_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \tilde{E}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \frac{\partial \varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_k} \quad (13a)$$

$$H_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \tilde{H}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_k} \quad (13b)$$

Combining the asymptotic expansions (11) (as well as other similar ones) with the differential equations (12) and the expressions (13a) and (13b) results in a series of four equations, called governing relations which can be used to determine the four, yet unknown functions, $u_k^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$, $T^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$, $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$ and $\psi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$ from which, all the field variables can be determined. One of these governing relations is given below:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \left\{ e_{ijk} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial u_j^{(1)}}{\partial y_k} - \varepsilon_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y_j} - \lambda_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y_j} - \Sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y_j} \right\} =$$

$$-\frac{\partial e_{ijk}}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial u_j^{(0)}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{E}_j^{(0)} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{ij}}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{H}_j^{(0)}$$

$$-\frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} T^{(0)} - \frac{\partial \Sigma_{ij}}{\partial y_i} \tilde{E}_j^{(0)} \quad (14)$$

It can be readily observed from the Eq. (14) as well as the remaining three governing relations, that, after taking the Laplace Transform (with respect to time), the right-hand side contains terms which are products of a function of y and a function of x . This separation of variables enables us to write down the solution of the four governing relations as follows:

$$\hat{u}_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = \hat{N}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)}{\partial x_l} + \hat{M}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{E}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) \quad (15)$$

$$+ \hat{N}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{H}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) + \hat{M}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{T}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)$$

$$\hat{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = \hat{\Lambda}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)}{\partial x_l} + \hat{Z}_k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{E}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) \quad (16)$$

$$+ \hat{\Gamma}_k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{H}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) + \hat{\Delta}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{T}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)$$

$$\hat{\psi}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = \hat{A}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)}{\partial x_l} + \hat{B}_k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{E}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) \quad (17)$$

$$+ \hat{\Xi}_k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{H}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell) + \hat{\Pi}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \hat{T}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)$$

$$\hat{T}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = \hat{\beta}_j(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \hat{T}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \ell)}{\partial x_j} \quad (18)$$

Here, quantities with a “hat”, for example $\hat{u}_j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell)$, represent the Laplace transform of $u_j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$ with “ ℓ ” being the Laplace parameter. We observe that Eqs. (15)-(18) contain 13 unknown functions, \hat{N}_i^{kl} , \hat{M}_i^k , \hat{N}_i^k , \hat{M}_i , $\hat{\Lambda}_{kl}$, \hat{Z}_k , $\hat{\Gamma}_k$, $\hat{\Delta}$, \hat{A}_{kl} , \hat{B}_k , $\hat{\Xi}_k$, $\hat{\Pi}$, and β_j (which is not a function of the Laplace variable). Their solutions are obtained by back-substitution of Eqs. (15)-(18) into the Laplace transform of the governing relations to obtain a set of 13 differential equations called “unit cell” problems that have the following form:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_j} = -\frac{\partial C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\tau}_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_j} = \frac{\partial e_{kij}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\chi}_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_j} = \frac{\partial Q_{kij}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\chi}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_j} = \frac{\partial \theta_{ij}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j} \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{d}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial e_{ikl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{v}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial \lambda_{ik}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i} \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{v}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial \xi_i(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\zeta}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial Q_{ikl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\zeta}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial \lambda_{ik}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\omega}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial \mu_{ik}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\omega}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial \xi_i(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i}; \quad \frac{\partial \hat{v}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial v_{ik}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_i} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{d}_i^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_i} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \left(\varepsilon_{ik}(\mathbf{y}) + \frac{1}{\ell} \Sigma_{ik} \right) \quad (25)$$

The quantities on the left-hand sides of Eqs. (19)-(25) depend on the material parameters of the smart composite as well as other functions such as $\hat{\tau}_{ij}^{kl}$. These latter functions are in turn defined in terms of the so-called “local functions” such as \hat{N}_i^{kl} that appear in Eqs. (15)-(18). For example, one can readily obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) = & C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \hat{N}_m^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_n} + e_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \hat{\Lambda}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_n} \\ & + Q_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \hat{A}_{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell)}{\partial y_n} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

2.3 Effective Coefficients

Following the derivation of the unit-cell problems, we are now in a position to calculate the first terms in the asymptotic expansions of the mechanical stress, electric displacement, magnetic field, current density and heat flux. To this end, from the Laplace transform of Eqs. (11), (13a), (13b) and the remaining asymptotic field expansions, in conjunction with Eqs. (15)-(18), we obtain the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\sigma}_{ij}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = & \{C_{ijkl} + \hat{\tau}_{ij}^{kl}\} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}}{\partial x_l} - \{e_{kij} - \hat{\tau}_{ij}^k\} \hat{E}_k^{(0)} + \\ & - \{Q_{kij} - \hat{\chi}_{ij}^k\} \hat{H}_k^{(0)} - \{\theta_{ij} - \hat{\chi}_{ij}\} \hat{T}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{D}_{ij}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = & \left\{ e_{ikl} + \hat{d}_i^{kl} + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{\Gamma}_i^{kl} \right\} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}}{\partial x_l} \\ & + \left\{ \varepsilon_{ij} + \hat{d}_{ij} + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{G}_{ij} \right\} \hat{E}_j^{(0)} + \left\{ \lambda_{ij} + \hat{v}_{ij} + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{I}_{ij} \right\} \hat{H}_k^{(0)} \\ & + \left\{ \xi_i + \hat{v}_i + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{O}_i \right\} \hat{T}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{B}_i^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = & \{Q_{ikl} + \hat{\zeta}_i^{kl}\} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}}{\partial x_l} + \{\lambda_{ij} + \hat{\zeta}_i^j\} \hat{E}_k^{(0)} \\ & + \{\mu_{ij} + \hat{\omega}_i^j\} \hat{H}_k^{(0)} + \{\eta_i + \hat{\omega}_i\} \hat{T}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{J}_{ij}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = & \{\hat{\Sigma}_{ik} - \hat{G}_{ik}\} \hat{E}_j^{(0)} + \\ & - \hat{F}_i^{kl} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k^{(0)}}{\partial x_l} - \hat{I}_{ik} \hat{H}_k^{(0)} - \hat{O}_i \hat{T}^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

$$\hat{q}_i^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \ell) = -\{V_{ij} + v_i^j(\mathbf{y})\} \frac{\partial \hat{T}^{(0)}}{\partial x_j} \quad (31)$$

We will now apply the homogenization procedure, which entails integration over the volume of the unit cell

$$\tilde{A} = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y A \, dV \quad (32)$$

to obtain the effective Laplace transform for stress, electric displacement, magnetic field, free conduction current and heat flux. Comparing the resulting expressions with the original constitutive equations in Eqs. (5)-(9) yields the effective coefficients. Therefore, from Eq. (27) we obtain the effective elastic coefficients, $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{ijkl}(\ell)$, piezoelectric, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{kij}(\ell)$, piezomagnetic, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{kij}(\ell)$, and thermal expansion coefficients, $\hat{\theta}_{ij}(\ell)$. They are given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{ijkl}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{C}_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{c}}_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (33a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{kij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{e}_{kij}(\mathbf{y}) - \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (33b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{kij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{Q}_{kij}(\mathbf{y}) - \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (33c)$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \theta_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) - \hat{\theta}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (33d)$$

Applying a similar procedure to Eq. (28) we obtain the effective piezoelectric, dielectric permittivity, magnetoelectric, and pyroelectric coefficients. They are, respectively, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{ikl}(\ell)$, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{ij}(\ell)$, $\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\ell)$, and $\hat{\xi}_i(\ell)$ and are given below in Eqs. (34a)-(34d). The latter two represent two of the aforementioned product properties.

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{ikl}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \left\{ \mathbf{e}_{ikl}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{ik}^l(\mathbf{y}, \ell) + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \right\} d\mathbf{V} \quad (34a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \left\{ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) + \frac{1}{\ell} \mathbf{G}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \right\} d\mathbf{V} \quad (34b)$$

$$\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \left\{ \lambda_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \right\} d\mathbf{V} \quad (34c)$$

$$\hat{\xi}_i(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \left\{ \xi_i(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell) + \frac{1}{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{O}}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \right\} d\mathbf{V} \quad (34d)$$

Similarly, applying the homogenization procedure to Eq. (29) and comparing with the corresponding constitutive equation (7), we obtain the effective piezomagnetic, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{ikl}(\ell)$, magnetoelectric, $\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\ell)$, magnetic permeability, $\hat{\mu}_{ij}(\ell)$, and pyromagnetic, $\hat{\eta}_i(\ell)$ coefficients. They are given in Eqs. (35a)-(35d).

$$\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{ikl}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{Q}_{ikl}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\mathbf{g}}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (35a)$$

$$\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \lambda_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\xi}_i^j(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (35b)$$

$$\hat{\mu}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mu_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\omega}_i^j(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (35c)$$

$$\hat{\eta}_i(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \eta_i(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{\omega}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (35d)$$

Homogenization of Eq. (30) yields the effective electrical conductivity, $\hat{\Sigma}_{ik}(\ell)$ and three new product properties, $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{kl}(\ell)$, $\hat{\mathbf{I}}_{ik}(\ell)$, $\hat{\mathbf{O}}_i(\ell)$. These latter properties relate the free conduction current to, respectively, the mechanical deformation, the magnetic field, and the temperature. They are absent from the original constitutive equation (8).

$$\hat{\Sigma}_{ik}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \Sigma_{ik}(\mathbf{y}) - \hat{\mathbf{G}}_{ik}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (36a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{kl}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{F}_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (36b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{I}}_{ik}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{I}_{ik}(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (36c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{O}}_i(\ell) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{Y}|} \int_{\mathbf{Y}} \{ \mathbf{O}_i(\mathbf{y}, \ell) \} d\mathbf{V} \quad (36d)$$

Finally, the effective thermal conductivity is obtained from Eq. (31) and is given by:

$$\hat{V}_{ij}(\ell) = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \{V_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) + \hat{V}_i^j(\mathbf{y}, \ell)\} dV \quad (37)$$

Before closing this Section it is worthwhile to note that both the unit-cell problems and the effective coefficients are solved entirely in the domain of the unit cell. As such, they are dependent only on the material and geometrical make-up of the unit cell and once determined they can be applied to any boundary-value problem pertaining to the given geometry.

3 Examples and Model Validation

3.1 Example 1

The developed model is applied to the practically important examples of the smart composite laminates. The first example pertains to the laminate shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Smart composite laminate and its unit cell

We will assume that the laminate consists of alternating laminae of piezoelectric (Barium Titanate) and piezomagnetic (Cobalt Ferrite) material. The volume fraction of the piezoelectric material is ϑ and that of the piezomagnetic is $(1 - \vartheta)$. The elastic, piezoelectric, etc. properties of these materials can be found in [8]. The materials are transversely isotropic with the x_3 direction being

both the axis of symmetry and the poling and magnetization direction.

Let us now proceed to the computation of the effective coefficients of this structure. Let us begin with the effective elastic coefficients. As Fig. 2 shows, for the structure under consideration, the only variation in material properties takes place in the y_1 direction. Consequently, the first unit cell problem in Eq. (19) can be reduced to:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\tau}_{il}^{km}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} = -\frac{\partial C_{i1km}(y_1)}{\partial y_1} \quad (38a)$$

where $\hat{\tau}_{il}^{km}$ is defined in Eq. (26). Integrating (38a) yields:

$$\hat{\tau}_{il}^{km}(y_1, \ell) = -C_{i1km}(y_1) + O_{il}^{km}(\ell) \quad (38b)$$

where $O_{il}^{km}(\ell)$ are the constants of integration. To calculate the effective elastic coefficient \tilde{C}_{11} we assume $i = k = m = 1$. Thus:

$$\hat{\tau}_{11}^{11}(y_1, \ell) = -C_{1111}(y_1) + O_{11}^{11}(\ell) \quad (38c)$$

As well, Eq. (26) reduces to:

$$\hat{\tau}_{11}^{11}(y_1, \ell) = C_{11m1}(y_1) \frac{\partial \hat{N}_m^{11}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} + e_{111}(y_1) \frac{\partial \hat{\Lambda}_{11}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} + Q_{111}(y_1) \frac{\partial \hat{A}_{11}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} \quad (38d)$$

Reference to the material properties in [8] will reveal that for the transversely isotropic BaTiO₃ and CoFe₂O₄ (around x_3 axis) e_{111} and Q_{111} are both zero. Furthermore, C_{1121} and C_{1131} are both zero. Consequently, Eq. (38d) reduces to:

$$\hat{\tau}_{11}^{11}(y_1, \ell) = C_{1111}(y_1) \frac{\partial \hat{N}_1^{11}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} \quad (38e)$$

From Eqs. (38c) and (38e) we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{N}_1^{11}(y_1, \ell)}{\partial y_1} = -1 + \frac{O_{11}^{11}(\ell)}{C_{1111}(y_1)} \quad (38f)$$

If we now integrate Eq. (38f) while considering at the same time the periodicity of \hat{N}_1^{11} we arrive at:

$$0 = -1 + \left[\frac{\vartheta}{C_{11}^{(e)}} + \frac{1-\vartheta}{C_{11}^{(m)}} \right] O_{11}^{11}(\ell) \quad (38g)$$

where the superscripts (m) and (e) refer to the piezomagnetic and piezoelectric constituent respectively. To calculate \tilde{C}_{11} we make use of Eq. (33a) which, for the problem at hand, reduces to:

$$\hat{C}_{11}(\ell) = \int_0^1 \{C_{1111}(y_1) + \hat{\tau}_{11}^{11}(y_1, \ell)\} dy_1 \quad (39a)$$

Thus,

$$\hat{C}_{11}(\ell) = \frac{C_{11}^{(e)}C_{11}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta)C_{11}^{(e)}} \quad (39b)$$

The last step in the procedure is to take the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (39b) to yield:

$$\tilde{C}_{11}(t) = \frac{C_{11}^{(e)}C_{11}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta)C_{11}^{(e)}} \delta(t) \quad (39c)$$

where $\delta(t)$ is the Dirac function. Integrating this expression over the entire spectrum of time yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}_{11} &= \int_{t=-\infty}^{t=\infty} \tilde{C}_{11}(t) dt = \int_{t=-\infty}^{t=\infty} \frac{C_{11}^{(e)}C_{11}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta)C_{11}^{(e)}} \delta(t) \\ &= \frac{C_{11}^{(e)}C_{11}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta)C_{11}^{(e)}} \end{aligned} \quad (39d)$$

The computation of the remaining elastic coefficients proceeds in much the same straightforward fashion with the notable exception of the coefficient \tilde{C}_{55} . For this coefficient, the procedure, though straightforward, is algebraically tedious. Details can be found in [8]. In the process, we obtain not only \tilde{C}_{55} but also the effective piezoelectric coefficient \tilde{e}_{15} and the piezomagnetic coefficient \tilde{Q}_{15} . The resulting expressions are too lengthy to be reproduced here but have the general form [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}_{55}(t) &= \kappa_1 e^{-\mu_1 t} + \kappa_2 e^{-\mu_2 t} + \kappa_3 e^{-\mu_3 t} + \kappa_4 \delta(t) \\ \tilde{e}_{15}(t) &= \kappa_5 e^{-\mu_4 t} + \kappa_6 e^{-\mu_5 t} + \kappa_7 e^{-\mu_6 t} + \kappa_8 \delta(t) \\ \tilde{Q}_{15}(t) &= \kappa_9 e^{-\mu_7 t} + \kappa_{10} e^{-\mu_8 t} + \kappa_{11} e^{-\mu_9 t} + \kappa_{12} \delta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (39d)$$

where $\kappa_i, i=1,2,\dots,12$ and $\mu_j, j=1,2,\dots,9$ are known functions which depend on the aforementioned material parameters of the piezoelectric and the piezomagnetic constituents of the unit cell. Overall, it is interesting to note that even though the original constituents both exhibit transverse isotropy with respect to x_3 axis, the effective macroscopic composite exhibits class mm2 symmetry as shown below [8]:

$$[C_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}_{11}(t) & \tilde{C}_{12}(t) & \tilde{C}_{13}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{12}(t) & \tilde{C}_{22}(t) & \tilde{C}_{23}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{C}_{13}(t) & \tilde{C}_{23}(t) & \tilde{C}_{33}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{44}(t) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{55}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{C}_{66}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

The determination of the effective piezoelectric, piezomagnetic and thermal expansion coefficients follows from the second unit cell problem in Eq. (19) and the unit cell problems in Eq. (20) taking into account the definitions (33b)-(33d). Following the same methodology as the one employed for the determination of the effective elastic coefficients, yields typical expressions for \tilde{e}_{31} , \tilde{Q}_{32} and $\tilde{\theta}_{22}$:

$$\tilde{e}_{31} = \frac{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} e_{31}^{(e)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{11}^{(e)}} \quad (41a)$$

$$\tilde{Q}_{32} = \frac{\left[\vartheta Q_{31}^{(e)} + (1-\vartheta) Q_{31}^{(m)} \right] + \frac{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} C_{12}^{(e)} Q_{31}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{12}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)} Q_{31}^{(e)}}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}}}{\vartheta C_{12}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{12}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}} \times \frac{\left[\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} Q_{31}^{(e)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{11}^{(e)} Q_{31}^{(m)} \right]}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}} \quad (41b)$$

$$\tilde{\theta}_{22} = \left[\begin{array}{l} \left[\vartheta \theta_{22}^{(e)} + (1-\vartheta) \theta_{22}^{(m)} \right] + \\ \frac{\vartheta C_{12}^{(e)} \theta_{11}^{(e)} e_{31}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{12}^{(m)} \theta_{11}^{(m)} e_{31}^{(e)}}{e_{31}^{(e)} e_{31}^{(m)}} \\ + \frac{\left(\vartheta \theta_{11}^{(e)} e_{31}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) \theta_{11}^{(m)} e_{31}^{(e)} \right)^2}{e_{31}^{(e)} e_{31}^{(m)} \left(\vartheta e_{31}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(e)} \right)} \end{array} \right] \quad (41c)$$

The remaining effective piezoelectric, thermal expansion and piezomagnetic coefficients will be presented graphically in the sequel.

The calculation of the effective dielectric permittivity, magnetic permeability, and electrical and thermal conductivity proceeds in much the same manner by starting from the appropriate unit cell problems. Some of these coefficients will be given graphically in the sequel.

Of particular interest in this work are the effective product properties. The methodology for obtaining them is of course the same as above and considers the appropriate unit cell problems and the expressions in Eqs. (34c), 34(d), 35(c), 35(d), (36b-36d). For example,

$$\tilde{\lambda}_{33} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\vartheta e_{31}^{(e)} Q_{31}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(m)} Q_{31}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}} + \\ \left[\frac{\vartheta Q_{31}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) Q_{31}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}} \right] X \\ \left[\frac{\vartheta e_{31}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{11}^{(e)}} \right] \end{array} \right\} \quad (42a)$$

$$\tilde{\zeta}_3^m = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\vartheta e_{31}^{(e)} \theta_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(m)} \theta_{11}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}} + \\ \left[\frac{\vartheta e_{31}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) e_{31}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{C_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)}} \right] X \\ \frac{\vartheta \theta_{11}^{(e)} C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) \theta_{11}^{(m)} C_{11}^{(e)}}{\vartheta C_{11}^{(m)} + (1-\vartheta) C_{11}^{(e)}} \end{array} \right\} \quad (42b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_{11}^3(t) &= \alpha_1 e^{-\sigma_1 t} + \alpha_2 e^{-\sigma_2 t} + \alpha_3 e^{-\sigma_3 t} + \alpha_4 \delta(t) \\ \tilde{I}_{11}(t) &= \alpha_5 e^{-\sigma_4 t} + \alpha_6 e^{-\sigma_5 t} + \alpha_7 e^{-\sigma_6 t} + \alpha_8 \delta(t) \\ \tilde{\lambda}_{11}(t) &= \alpha_9 e^{-\sigma_7 t} + \alpha_{10} e^{-\sigma_8 t} + \alpha_{11} e^{-\sigma_9 t} + \alpha_{12} \delta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (42c)$$

where $\alpha_i, i=1,2,\dots,12$ and $\sigma_j, j=1,2,\dots,9$ are known functions which depend on $C_{55}, e_{15}, Q_{15}, \varepsilon_{11}$ and μ_{11} parameters of the piezoelectric and the piezomagnetic constituents of the unit cell. The quantities in Eq. (42c) would then have to be integrated in the manner of Eq. (39d). The resulting expressions are too lengthy to be reproduced here.

Fig. 3 shows the variation of the effective elastic properties of the composite vs. the volume fraction of Barium Titanate. It is seen that most of the effective coefficients non-linearly decrease with an increase in the volume fraction of the piezoelectric phase because the corresponding properties of this constituent are lower than those of its counterpart.

Fig. 3. Effective elastic coefficients vs. volume fraction of BaTiO₃

Fig. 4. Effective piezoelectric coefficients vs. volume fraction of BaTiO₃

Figs. 4, 5 and 6 show, respectively, variations of the effective piezoelectric, magnetoelectric and pyroelectric coefficients vs. the volume fraction BaTiO₃. As expected, increasing the volume fraction of the piezoelectric layer results in a corresponding increase (in the absolute value sense) in the values of the effective piezoelectric coefficients. Figs. 5 and 6 illustrate the strongly non-linear variation of the effective magnetoelectric and pyroelectric product properties with the volume fraction of Barium Titanate. For the particular example under consideration, these product properties maximize themselves at a Barium Titanate volume fraction of around 0.4.

Fig. 5. Effective magnetoelectric coefficients vs. volume fraction of BaTiO₃

Fig. 6. Effective pyroelectric coefficient $\tilde{\xi}_3$ vs. volume fraction of BaTiO₃

The practical importance of the present work lies in the fact that the model can be used to tailor the

effective properties of a particular laminate by changing certain geometric and/or material parameters of the unit cell. It is thus of significant practical importance to engineering design.

3.2 Quasistatic Model – Comparison of Models

The micromechanical model presented in this paper was derived on the basis of dynamic force balance and the time-varying form of Maxwell's equations. In the absence of inertia forces and free conduction currents it is possible to derive a similar model based on static equilibrium and the quasi-static approximation of Maxwell's equations [7]. Such a model may be referred to as the quasi-static model and the pertinent governing equations have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij} \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right)}{\partial x_j} &= f_i \text{ on } G \quad \text{with } \mathbf{u} \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right) = 0 \text{ on } \partial G \\ \frac{\partial D_i \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right)}{\partial x_i} &= 0 \text{ on } G \quad \text{with } \mathbf{D} \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right) = 0 \text{ on } \partial G \\ \frac{\partial B_i \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right)}{\partial x_i} &= 0 \text{ on } G \quad \text{with } \mathbf{B} \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right) = 0 \text{ on } \partial G \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Here, f_i represent body forces. Furthermore, the irrotational electric and magnetic fields may be written down as gradients of electric and magnetic potentials [7]:

$$E_i \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right) = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i}, \quad H_i \left(\mathbf{x}, \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\varepsilon} \right) = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_i} \quad (44)$$

Following the methodology of Sections 2.2 and 2.3 it is possible to derive a new set of unit cell problems and different expressions for the effective coefficients [7]. For example, two of these unit cell problems are given below:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j} = -\frac{\partial C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j}; \quad \frac{\partial \lambda_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j} = -\frac{\partial e_{kij}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_j} \quad (45)$$

Here, the functions $\tau_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y})$ and $\lambda_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y})$ are given by:

$$\tau_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) = C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial N_m^{kl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} + e_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial L_{kl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} + Q_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial R_{kl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} \quad (46a)$$

$$\tilde{\lambda}_{ij}^k(\mathbf{y}) = C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial P_{mk}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} + e_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \Psi_k(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} + Q_{nij}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \Gamma_k(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} \quad (46b)$$

The remaining unit cell problems and associated definitions can be found in [7]. One observes that the unit-cell problems pertaining to the quasi-static model are not functions of the Laplace variable since the original governing and constitutive equations are not functions of time.

If we then apply the obtained results to the laminate considered in Example 1, we will see that the two models conform exactly with one another except in the case of six effective coefficients \tilde{C}_{55} , \tilde{e}_{15} , \tilde{Q}_{15} , $\tilde{\epsilon}_{11}$, $\tilde{\mu}_{11}$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_{11}$. Not surprisingly, these are the effective coefficients that contain the exponential terms in the dynamic model. The results of the quasi-static model also agree with the works of other researchers, see [6].

3.3 Example 2

We will now consider a different laminate in which the poling and magnetization directions are perpendicular to the interphase, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Smart composite laminate (perpendicular connectivity) and its unit cell

For the sake of convenience we will assume that the constituents are the same as in Example 1. For Example 2 we will apply the quasi-static model.

As Fig. 7 shows, for the structure under consideration, the only variation in material properties takes place in y_3 direction. Consequently, the first unit cell-problem in Eq. (45) reduces to:

$$\frac{d\tau_{i3}^{kl}(y_3)}{dy_3} = -\frac{dC_{i3kl}(y_3)}{dy_3} \quad (47a)$$

Integrating this expression with respect to y_3 yields:

$$\tau_{i3}^{kl}(y_3) = -C_{i3kl}(y_3) + O_{i3}^{kl} \quad (47b)$$

where O_{i3}^{kl} are constants of integration. Letting $i = l$ and $k, l = 3$ results in:

$$\tau_{13}^{13}(y_3) = -C_{1313}(y_3) + O_{13}^{13} \quad (47c)$$

Expression (46a) now becomes:

$$\tau_{13}^{13}(y_3) = C_{13m3}(y_3) \frac{dN_m^{13}(y_3)}{dy_3} + e_{313}(y_3) \frac{dL_{kl}(y_3)}{dy_3} + Q_{313}(y_3) \frac{dR_{kl}(y_3)}{dy_3} \quad (47d)$$

For the transversely isotropic constituents under consideration, e_{313} , Q_{313} , C_{1323} and C_{1333} vanish [8]. Thus, Eq. (47d) reduces to:

$$\tau_{13}^{13}(y_3) = C_{1313}(y_3) \frac{dN_1^{13}(y_3)}{dy_3} \quad (47e)$$

Combination of Eqs. (47d) and (47e) results in:

$$\tau_{13}^{13}(y_3) = -C_{55}(y_3) + \frac{C_{55}^{(e)} C_{55}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{55}^{(m)} + (1 - \vartheta) C_{55}^{(e)}} \quad (47f)$$

Finally, applying Eq. (33a) to Eq. (47f) yields the effective \tilde{C}_{55} coefficient:

$$\tilde{C}_{55} = \frac{C_{55}^{(e)} C_{55}^{(m)}}{\vartheta C_{55}^{(m)} + (1 - \vartheta) C_{55}^{(e)}} \quad (47g)$$

The remaining effective coefficients can be obtained in the similar manner. The results of the quasi-static model in general and this example in particular conform to those obtained by Bravo-Castillero et al [6], who used the periodic unfolding homogenization technique.

Before delving into the next example, it should be mentioned here that the effective properties calculated are associated with a thick laminate (since the underlying models are 3D models). The preponderance of uses of composite materials today however, is in the form of thin laminated plates and shells. For example, the effective elastic coefficients should be classified into the familiar extensional, bending and coupling elastic coefficients, (similar considerations apply to other effective coefficients). Consequently, if one is interested in analyzing thin laminates, another paper of the authors becomes pertinent, see Hadjiloizi et al [9].

3.4 Example 3

This example deals with the micromechanical analysis and determination of the effective elastic coefficients of network reinforced composites such as the structure shown in Fig. 8, see [12].

Fig. 8. 3D Grid-reinforced composite structure with reinforcements arranged in a rhombic fashion [12].

For the purposes of this example, let us assume that we are only interested in determining the effective elastic coefficients of the network structure in which

the stiff reinforcements are embedded in a soft matrix. The unit cell problem associated with this structure is given by the first expression in Eq. (45). The local functions $\tau_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y})$ are defined in Eq. (46a) and, after omitting extra terms, are:

$$\tau_{ij}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) = C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial N_m^{kl}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_n} \quad (48)$$

Briefly, the procedure involved in analyzing this problem entails the consideration of a simple unit-cell with only a single arbitrarily oriented reinforcement, performing a coordinate transformation which reorients one axis to coincide with the reinforcement (a procedure which reduces an inherently 3D problem to a 2D one) and finally obtaining the effective elastic coefficients of multi-fiber unit cells via superposition, see Hassan et al [12].

Fig. 9. Variation of the effective stiffness modulus, \tilde{E}_3 , for the structure of Fig. 8 [12]

The results for the effective Young's Modulus \tilde{E}_3 are shown in Fig. 9 alongside corresponding values obtained via the Finite Element Method (FEM). Two FEM plots are shown; one neglects the (soft) matrix properties and the other is a complete FEM model with both the matrix and the reinforcement properties taken into consideration. It is readily observed that the results from asymptotic homogenization model conform quite well to their counterparts from the finite element technique.

Conclusions

Two comprehensive micromechanical models for the analysis of piezo-magneto-thermo-elastic smart composite structures are developed and applied to examples of practical importance. The first model is based on dynamic equilibrium, Maxwell's equations and thermal balance while the second model employs static force balance and the quasi-static approximation of Maxwell's equations. Both models derive general relations called unit cell problems. They can be used to determine the effective elastic, piezoelectric, piezomagnetic, thermal expansion, dielectric permittivity, magnetic permeability, magnetoelectric, pyroelectric and pyromagnetic coefficients. The latter three sets of coefficients are particularly interesting in the sense that they represent the so-called product properties.

The results of the two models and the use of the effective coefficients are illustrated by means of three practically important examples. The first two examples pertain to laminates consisting of transversely isotropic piezoelectric and piezomagnetic constituents. It is observed that in this instance the results from the two models conform very well to one another with the exception of six effective coefficients; \tilde{C}_{55} , \tilde{e}_{55} , \tilde{Q}_{55} , $\tilde{\epsilon}_{11}$, $\tilde{\mu}_{11}$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_{11}$. As well, the results of the quasi-static model agree with the works of other researchers.

The third example pertained to the determination of the effective elastic coefficients of 3D network reinforced composites with a periodic grid of stiff reinforcements embedded in a soft matrix. It is readily seen that the results from the asymptotic homogenization models conform quite well to their counterparts from the finite element technique.

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